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GRAVITATIONAL WAVES

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Abstract

Scientific research work "Gravitational Waves" by Dmytro Pavlovych Poliak, a student of Lybid Gymnasium No. 34 named after V. Maksymenko in Kyiv.

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Objective: Analysis of data from gravitational wave signals on gravitational interferometers. Search for sources of gravitational waves in the visible range.

Relevance

As I have mentioned earlier, there is something worth thinking about, and perhaps this became the main reason. In this work, I will convey all the known information about gravitational waves, all theories and assumptions, and also conduct a data analysis. For a deeper understanding of this topic, I joined the GRANDMA project, which explores the nature of gravitational waves at a very high level. I believe that gravitational waves are a new trend in contemporary and future astrophysics.

Gravitational waves are an extremely interesting object to observe. Thanks to gravitational waves, we can discover new astronomical objects. Also, gravitational waves have been able to confirm many scientific theories, such as the general theory of relativity and the theory of the big bang. I believe that gravitational waves will help us better understand the Universe and may even bring scientists closer to creating new theories (such as the theory of everything).

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INTRODUCTION

In the introduction, I have chosen to elucidate why I opted for this particular topic.

Relevance

As I have previously mentioned, there is much to contemplate, and perhaps this became the primary reason. In this work, I will convey all the known information about gravitational waves, encompassing theories and assumptions, and I will also conduct a data analysis. For a deeper understanding of this topic, I have joined the GRANDMA project, which investigates the nature of gravitational waves at a highly advanced level. I believe that gravitational waves represent a new trend in contemporary and future astrophysics.

Gravitational waves are an extraordinarily intriguing object that demands observation. Thanks to gravitational waves, we can discover new astronomical objects. Additionally, gravitational waves have been instrumental in reaffirming numerous scientific theories, such as the general theory of relativity and the theory of the big bang. I am of the opinion that gravitational waves will assist us in better comprehending the Universe, and perhaps even draw scientists closer to the creation of new theories (such as the theory of everything).

Objective: Analysis of data from gravitational wave signals on gravitational interferometers. Search for sources of gravitational waves in the visible range.

Tasks:

1. Analyze all data on gravitational waves known at the moment.
2. Extract parameters of gravitational waves necessary for their registration.
3. Participate in the program to search for sources of gravitational waves in the visible range.

Research Object: Gravitational waves.

Subject of Research: Detection of gravitational waves, search for their sources in the visible range.

Research Methods: Analysis and systematization of theoretical data, comparison, observation of galaxies.

Scientific Novelty: Gravitational waves were first directly detected in 2016. Also, in this work, I have formulated my own perspective on certain theoretical aspects of gravitational wave research.

Practical Value: Participated in the international company for the search and research of gravitational wave sources - GRANDMA.

CHAPTER 1 GRAVITATIONAL WAVES PART ONE

1.1. Nature of Gravitational Waves

Gravitational waves are disturbances in the gravitational field that propagate through the spacetime continuum in the form of waves at the speed of light. Albert Einstein first predicted them in 1916 in his famous general theory of relativity. Gravitational waves are generated by any massive body that undergoes rapid motion in space or by two massive bodies interacting. However, capturing gravitational waves proved to be an extremely challenging task, as, according to calculations, the masses of interacting bodies must be incredibly large, and the bodies themselves sufficiently compact in size [3, 7, 11].

Similar to electromagnetic radiation, gravitational waves, according to the general theory of relativity, propagate at the speed of light and carry energy in the form of gravitational radiation. Within the framework of Newton's law of universal gravitation, gravitational waves cannot exist because this law is based on the assumption that physical interactions propagate at an infinite speed. Despite a well-known series of experimental confirmations of the general theory of relativity, gravitational waves remained elusive until recently.

Gravitational waves are a unique oscillation of spacetime emanating from massive objects in accelerated motion. The simplest way to visualize such a wave is to observe its effect on freely moving material points initially positioned in a ring. A sinusoidal gravitational wave propagating through such a ring normal to its plane deforms it (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Deformation in the arrangement of material points caused by the passage of gravitational waves perpendicular to the plane of the figure. Since such deformation can occur in different directions, the concept of polarization of gravitational waves exists.

Due to the relative weakness of gravitational waves, their detection is challenging, as among the four known fundamental interactions today, gravity is the weakest. If electromagnetic interaction is considered to be 1, gravitational interaction is only on the order of 10^{-40} . It is well-known that an electric charge in accelerated motion is a source of

electromagnetic waves, which are easily detectable. However, the amplitude of gravitational waves is very small and is determined by the parameter h , which is dimensionless and essentially measures the relative expansion or compression of space caused by the passage of these waves. Gravitational waves passing through the Earth have an amplitude that does not exceed $h \sim 10^{-20}$. For instance, based on Figure 1, the amplitude of gravitational waves would reach $A \sim 0.5$, making the experimental challenges of their detection evident [8, 9, 15].

1.2. How Can We Detect Them

Imagine that you need to find an enemy submarine in neutral waters. This is done as follows: microphones are placed in a certain area, and they are very sensitive. Of course, you want to detect the submarine as far away from the microphones as possible. You cannot cover the entire sea with microphones; you can only cover a certain area. These microphones pick up sounds from ships, dolphins, and whales—everything that makes sounds, and these sounds are often stronger than those emitted by a distant submarine. How can you then see it?

It turns out that the military, from "experimental data," know what the engine of a particular submarine sounds like—that is, the characteristic sound it leaves behind. Accordingly, they know the characteristic curve that the submarine will produce on the microphone. The microphones are placed at a certain distance. The signal picked up by the microphones, the curve, must be seen with some precision on all or a certain number of microphones. Also, the signals that reach the microphones must be separated by some time interval, no more than the distance between the microphones divided by the speed of sound. So, if one microphone hears a sound, and another sees the same curve, and the time interval between these two signals exceeds a certain limit, it is just a coincidence, not a real situation.

If the submarine is passing by at a distance, this sound on two microphones looks like a wave on a large sound wave coming from all sides. The microphone signals are sent to a computer, and it analyzes them. If several microphones see a curve, and the curves coincide with some accuracy, special programs recognize the agreement between these curves. If you have a grid of microphones arranged in a certain way, you can even determine at what distance, in which direction, and where the submarine passed.

Gravity waves are detected in the same way. At least two microphones are needed, but more are preferable. Currently, two are operational, located in the United States at different ends of the country, at a distance of 3500–4000 kilometers from each other. One is in the Florida region, and the other is in the Washington state region in the northwest. These microphones must pick up the signal. Moreover, it should be the same signal, meaning there must be agreement between the curves. And they should be separated by a time interval no more than the distance between these two detectors divided by the speed of light. The maximum time occurs if the wave comes to one detector and goes straight along the line between these two detectors. But the wave can also come to them simultaneously if it comes from above.

You have two enormous detectors, for example, the Michelson-Morley interferometer, with each arm measuring 4 kilometers, intersecting in the shape of an inverted letter 'L'. If a gravitational wave directly hits this detector vertically, the arms of this detector start to oscillate, meaning one arm elongates while the other contracts. Then vice versa: one elongates, the other contracts, and so on [1-3, 14, 16, 22].

How can you see that the arms are oscillating? The Michelson-Morley detector is arranged to observe interference. Electromagnetic waves travel along both arms, and then the detector collects the signal from these two arms. It's crucial to achieve the practical cancellation of waves from both arms. That is, you set up a situation where you practically have zero signal on the detector [13]. In each arm, you should have a whole number of half-waves, so when nothing is happening on the detector, they completely cancel each other out. Now, if your arms start oscillating, the waves no longer completely cancel out, but begin to shift, and you get a signal on the detector. You need a rotating mechanism, adjusting mirrors that reflect light so that the signal is zero. Essentially, you need to measure the current in this mechanism, which adjusts, and the current is measured with great precision. The signal from gravitational waves is ripples against the background of these oscillations. See Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the Michelson laser interferometer used for detecting gravitational waves.

How do they know the signal they need to observe? There are no "experimental data" for it. The data come from computer simulations. Several hundred samples are simulated on the computer: different mergers of black holes of various sizes with different rotation angles, mergers from various distances to each other, mergers of neutron stars, neutron stars and black holes. Therefore, scientists approximately knew the characteristic shape of the curve they should see.

1.3. Objects Emitting Gravitational Waves

Obtaining gravitational waves from any Earthly sources is unrealistic, as it requires gigantic masses and enormous power to set them in motion, making this task technically unfeasible. The situation becomes more favorable when cosmic objects are the sources of gravitational waves, where giant masses and tremendous rotational speeds are naturally provided. Among them, binary stars rotating around a common center of mass and pulsars, which are rotating neutron stars, are most suitable [5, 16, 19, 20]. The energy of gravitational radiation from these sources is immense; however, they are located at significant distances from Earth (tens or hundreds of light-years), and only a very small fraction of their gravitational radiation reaches us.

In addition to periodic gravitational radiation from binary stars and pulsars, powerful bursts (pulses) of radiation can be observed from various cosmic cataclysms, such as flashes from supernovae leading to the formation of neutron stars or black holes, or during their collisions. The gravitational radiation flux arising during a supernova flash is approximately 10^{15} times greater than the flux from the nearest binary star. In our Galaxy, supernovae occur, on average, once every 30 years. Therefore, one should also expect to receive radiation from other galaxies: a sphere with a radius of nearly 10 million light-years contains approximately 300 galaxies, and pulses of gravitational radiation with a flux density of 10^{-3} W/cm² are expected to arrive several times a year. However, this magnitude is at the sensitivity limit, and detecting such bursts of gravitational waves is challenging [21, 22].

Stars are most often born not individually but in pairs. For example, let a pair of two massive stars be formed. Then both of them exploded sequentially as supernovae, giving two black holes, and they orbit each other. Let's imagine two balls rolling on our rubber surface; ripples will inevitably appear from them. In the case of a pair of black holes, this is a very favorable process for emitting gravitational waves, as we immediately have large masses, compactly arranged, and moving at enormous speeds.

If we take any object and throw it into a black hole, it crosses the horizon at the speed of light. This means it has a colossal speed and energy at that moment. Now, let's imagine such an extreme case: we take one black hole and throw it into another black hole. A lot of energy should be released, and it is released. But in what form? All this enormous energy is emitted in the form of gravitational waves. If two black holes merge in a system, a very powerful gravitational wave signal is generated [7, 10, 16].

Kilonova (other names: macronova, supernova r-process) is an astronomical event of the merger of two neutron stars or a neutron star and a black hole. The event is accompanied by powerful electromagnetic radiation associated with the decay of heavy elements formed due to r-processes, usually heavier than ⁵⁶Fe. These processes occur in practically isotropic emissions, analogous to a weak supernova with a short lifespan.

Fig. 4. Graphic representation of the process of detecting gravitational waves.

1.4. How They Were Detected

The first gravitational wave antenna, in the form of an aluminum cylinder several meters long, was constructed by the American scientist Joseph Weber. He later claimed to have detected gravitational waves. However, his results were questionable as Weber's instrument's sensitivity was millions of times worse than that of current detectors. Nonetheless, Weber inspired other researchers to delve into gravitational waves, leading to continued searches and significant improvements in detector sensitivity. It is unrealistic to obtain gravitational waves from any terrestrial sources, as it would require gigantic masses and immense power to set them in motion, making this technical challenge unfeasible. The situation becomes more favorable when cosmic objects serve as sources of gravitational waves, especially binary stars rotating around a common center of mass and pulsars—neutron stars that rotate. The energy of gravitational radiation from these sources is colossal, but they are located at such significant distances from Earth (tens or hundreds of light-years) that only a very small portion of their gravitational radiation reaches us.

“Rumor of a gravitational wave detection at LIGO detector. Amazing if true. Will post details if it survives.”

Lawrence M. Krauss

11:39 PM, September 25, 2015

GW150914 - FIRST DIRECT DETECTION OF GRAVITATIONAL WAVES

On February 11, 2016, the scientific collaboration of LIGO and the Virgo collaboration announced the first confirmed observation of gravitational waves resulting from the collision of black holes. The gravitational wave signals were observed by the dual LIGO observatories on September 14, 2015.

Fig.5. The signal observed by each LIGO detector.

These graphs depict the gravitational wave signals detected by the dual LIGO observatories in Livingston, Louisiana, and Hanford, Washington. The signals originated from two merging black holes, each approximately 30 times the mass of our Sun, located at a distance of 1.3 billion light-years [4-5, 13, 14].

The top two graphs show data obtained in Livingston and Hanford, along with the predicted waveforms. These predicted waveforms illustrate how two merging black holes should appear according to Albert Einstein's general theory of relativity equations, alongside the constantly present instrument noise. Time is plotted on the X-axis, and strain on the Y-axis. Strain represents the partial quantity distorted at a distance. As indicated by the segments, LIGO data closely align with Einstein's predictions.

The final plot compares data from both detectors. Hanford's data were inverted for comparison due to the difference in detector orientations at the two sites. The data were also shifted to correct for the time delay of gravitational wave signals between Livingston and Hanford (initially, the signal reached Livingston and then, moving at the speed of light, reached Hanford after seven thousandths of a second). As the plot demonstrates, both detectors witnessed the same event, confirming the detection.

Fig.6. Approximate location of GW150914 on the map of the southern hemisphere sky.

Colored lines represent different probabilities of the signal's origin: the purple line defines the region from which the signal is expected to originate with 90% accuracy; the inner yellow line delineates the target area with 10% accuracy. Gravitational waves were created by the merger of two black holes located 1.3 billion light-years away [4].

A small galaxy near ours, known as the Large Magellanic Cloud, can be seen as a blurred droplet beneath the marked area, while an even smaller galaxy called the Small Magellanic Cloud is positioned below it.

Researchers were able to 'visit' the location of the gravitational wave source using data from the LIGO observatories in Livingston, Louisiana, and Hanford, Washington. Gravitational waves arrived at Livingston 7 milliseconds before reaching Hanford. This time delay pinpointed a specific slice of the sky, or a ring, from which the signal likely originated. Further analysis of the signal's strength on both detectors ruled out portions of the ring, leaving the remainder depicted on this map.

Fig.7. Image of computer modeling showing the merger of two black holes.

LIGO detected gravitational waves, or ripples in space and time, generated as black holes spiraled, approached, collided, and merged. This simulation illustrates how the merger might appear to our eyes if we could somehow travel on a spacecraft for a closer observation. It was created by solving equations from Albert Einstein's general theory of relativity using LIGO data [9].

Stars appear distorted due to the incredibly strong gravity of the black holes. Black holes warp space and time, causing starlight to bend around them in a process known as gravitational lensing.

Fig. 8. Network of gravitational wave observatories during the first observation by LIGO.

During the detection of GW150914, the instruments of the global network included the paired LIGO detectors in Hanford, Washington, and Livingston, Louisiana, as well as GEO600 in Germany. The Virgo detector in Italy and the Kamioka Gravitational Wave Detector (KAGRA) in Japan were undergoing upgrades and were expected to start operating in 2016 and 2018, respectively. A sixth observatory is planned in India. Having more gravitational wave observatories worldwide helps scientists determine the locations and sources of gravitational waves coming from space [12].

Table 1. Main Parameters of the Gravitational Wave GW150914

Date:	September 14, 2015
Universal Time:	09:50:45
Distance to the GW Source:	1.3 billion light-years
Relative Space Deformation (Gravitational Wave Amplitude):	10^{-21}
Duration of GW Signal:	150 ms
Peak Duration of GW Signal:	15 ms

Frequency Range:	35—250 Hz
Frequency of Spectrum Maximum:	150 Hz
Wavelength Range:	900—8600 km
Maximum Frequency Growth Rate:	6—10 kHz/s
Binary Black Hole Mass (in Solar masses):	29+36
Black Hole Mass after Merger (in Solar masses):	62
GW Energy:	5.4×10^{47} J
Average GW Power:	3.6×10^{48} W
Peak GW Power:	3.6×10^{49} W
Average Energy Flux of GW:	2 mW/m ²
Maximum Energy Flux of GW:	20 mW/m ²
Efficiency of GW Radiator:	4.8%

CHAPTER 2

GRAVITATIONAL WAVES PART TWO

2.1. GRANDMA

Hunting for Gravitational Waves at the Foresters Observatory

The Department of Astronomy and Space Physics and the Department of Nuclear Physics at Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv participated in the third observational campaign of the LIGO and Virgo gravitational wave observatories.

The AZT-8 (70 cm) telescope of the Foresters Observatory is part of the international GRANDMA network, contributing to coordinated observations of GW sources on a global scale, including a citizen science program (Kilonova Catcher). It observed dozens of galaxies potentially undergoing collisions of binary neutron stars. It also identified a specific transient, AT2019wxt,

suspected to be associated with a GW event but eventually characterized as a supernova due to the explosion of a binary star.

Furthermore, archival searches for gamma-ray bursts were conducted using data from the Fermi-GBM and INTEGRAL-SPI space missions to find possible associations with GW sources.

During the eleven-month campaign, the analysis of optical and gamma-ray images did not reveal any counterparts to gravitational wave sources. However, thanks to rapid observations conducted by the Foresters Observatory, the limits achieved by the AZT-8 observations constrained the mass ejected during and after the collision.

Thanks to global efforts, the Foresters Observatory and its GRANDMA partners are well-prepared for the upcoming observation runs of LIGO and Virgo, where an increase in alert speed is expected. May the sun never set on this collaboration.

Table 1. Summary of GRANDMA Observations During the First Six Months for GW Candidates. Observations were not continuous. S190829u was retracted by the LIGO-Virgo collaboration due to data quality issues. 90% c.r. corresponds to the 90% credible region of the last sky localization area sent by LIGO-Virgo, δt to the delay from the gravitational wave trigger, ΔT to the observation duration, Prob (%), grad2 area for GRANDMA coverage compared to the latest sky localization review in percentage and square degrees. From May 19, 2019, to June 2, 2019, TRE and TCH were under technical maintenance, and on-site conditions for TCA were poor. S190924h was not observed due to lunar constraints. Δt depends on the delay of the first sky localization area sent by LVC.

	(UTC)		(Mpc)	(deg ²)		(h)	(h)	(%)	(deg ²)	
S190930s	13:35:41	MG (95%)	709 ± 191	1748	GRANDMA	1.9	57.0	17-18	19.0	260
					TCA	4.4	55.2	18	5.1	68
					TCH	12.7	46.0	18	3.0	38
					TRE	1.9	31.4	17	18.0	242
S190924h	02:19:258	MG (99%)	548 ± 112	303	No observations					
S190915ak	23:57:02	BBH (99%)	1584 ± 381	318	GRANDMA	0.3	50.7	18	36.1	80
					TCA	0.3	50.7	18	36.1	80
S190828l	06:55:09	BBH (99%)	1528 ± 387	359	GRANDMA	1.2	49.7	17-18	12.6	294
					TCA	12.6	31.2	18	0.3	67
					TCH	1.2	49.7	18	11.5	69
					TRE	14.2	23.7	17	0.8	157
S190828j	06:34:05	BBH (99%)	1946 ± 388	228	GRANDMA	0.5	47.6	17-18	6.1	210
					TCA	12.5	31.3	18	2.7	67
					TCH	0.5	47.6	18	0.04	21
					TRE	15.6	23.4	17	3.4	122
S190728q	06:45:10	MG (52%)	874 ± 171	104	GRANDMA	0.5	50.2	17-18	88.3	180
					TCA	13.2	29.6	18	18.8	26
					TCH	0.5	50.2	18	23.2	56
					TRE	10.5	22.6	17	83.3	121
S190727h	06:03:33	BBH (92%)	2839 ± 655	151	GRANDMA	1.5	163.8	17-18	49.0	138
					TCH	1.6	163.8	18	48.4	68
					TRE	16.7	17.2	17	0.7	70
S190720a	00:08:36	BBH (99%)	869 ± 283	443	GRANDMA	0.3	30.8	17-18	11.0	161
					TCA	0.6	26.8	18	5.0	60
					TCH	1.7	29.4	18	4.0	50
					TRE	0.3	22.7	17	4.0	71

S190707q	09:33:26	BBH (99%)	781 ± 211	921	GRANDMA	5.7	14.1	17-18	14.6	128
					TCA	10.7	6.1	18	2.4	21
					TCH	13.4	6.3	18	4.0	25
					TRE	5.7	4.8	17	9.5	88
S190706ai	22:26:41	BBH (99%)	5263 ± 1402	826	GRANDMA	0.5	22.9	17-18	16.0	167
					TCA	0.6	22.7	18	0.27	22
					TCH	0.5	9.1	18	3.9	24
					TRE	3.2	2.0	17	11.8	121
S190701ah	20:33:06	BBH (93%)	1849 ± 446	49	GRANDMA	2.7	2.9	17	41.7	71
					TRE	2.7	2.9	17	41.7	71
S190630ag	18:52:05	BBH (94%)	926 ± 259	1483	GRANDMA	4.7	18.9	17-18	11.4	92
					TCA	4.7	3.0	18	8.9	21
					TRE	21.0	2.5	17	2.5	71
S190602aq	17:59:27	BBH (99%)	797 ± 238	1172	No observations					
S190521r	07:43:59	BBH (99%)	1136 ± 279	488	No observations					
S190521g	03:02:29	BBH (97%)	3931 ± 953	765	No observations					
S190519bj	15:35:44	BBH (96%)	3154 ± 791	967	No observations					
S190517h ^a	05:51:01	BBH (98%)	2950 ± 1038	939	GRANDMA	4.2	17.3	18	8.9	11
					TCH	4.2	17.3	18	8.9	11
S190513bm ^a	20:54:28	BBH (94%)	1987 ± 501	691	GRANDMA	0.7	12.9	18	23.5	45
					TCA	0.7	5.6	18	7.0	24
					TCH	6.0	7.5	18	16.7	21
S190512at	18:07:14	BBH (99%)	1388 ± 322	252	GRANDMA	13.8	18.1	18	30.3	42
					TCA	25.5	5.8	18	7.2	22
					TCH	13.8	18.1	18	24	24
S190503bf ^a	18:54:04	BBH (96%)	421 ± 105	448	GRANDMA	4.3	4.7	18	17.1	24
					TCH	4.3	4.7	18	17.1	24
S190421ar	21:38:56	BBH (97%)	1628 ± 535	1444	GRANDMA	19.7	8.2	17	18.0	124
					TRE	19.7	8.2	17	18.0	124
S190412m ^a	05:30:44	BBH (100%)	812 ± 194	156	GRANDMA	10.1	12.2	17-18	75.9	125
					TCA	14.1	8.2	18	36.3	24
					TRE	10.1	7.7	17	73.4	123
S190408an ^a	18:18:02	BBH (100%)	1473 ± 358	387	No observations					

Table 2. Summary of GRANDMA Observations During the First Six Months for Binary Neutron Star or Neutron Star-Black Hole Merger Candidates, Using the Latest Versions of LALInference Sky Localization. Observations were not continuous throughout the entire time. S190518bb, S190524q, S190808ae, S190816i, S190822c were retracted by the LIGO-Virgo collaboration due to data quality issues in the detectors. 90% c.r. corresponds to the 90% credible region of the last sky localization area sent by LIGO-Virgo, δt to the delay from the GW trigger, ΔT to the observation duration, Prob (%), grad2 area for GRANDMA coverage compared to the latest sky localization review in percentage and square degrees. δt depends on the delay of the first sky localization area sent by the LIGO-Virgo collaboration, usually taking a few hours at the beginning of the campaign [30].

	(UTC)		(Mpc)	(deg ²)		(h)	(h)	(%)	(deg ²)	
S190930t ^a	14:34:07	NSBH (74%)	108 ± 38	24220	GRANDMA	1.0	80.5	17-18	1.3	250
					TCA	3.5	80.0	18	0.7	135
					TCH	11.9	71.5	18	0.6	110
					TRE	1.0	80.5	17	0.4	94
S190923y ^a	12:55:59	NSBH (68%)	438 ± 133	2107	GRANDMA	3.6	55.6	17-18	25.4	436
					TCA	5.5	46.3	18	2.2	64
					TCH	10.7	32.7	18	3.5	64
					TRE	3.6	55.6	17	20.0	312

S190910h	08:29:58	BNS (61%)	230 ± 88	24264	GRANDMA	10.5	129.1	18	1.1	337
					TCA	10.5	129.1	18	0.5	175
					TCH	25.0	113.1	18	0.6	161
S190910d	01:26:19	NSBH (98%)	632 ± 186	2482	GRANDMA	1.0	67.6	17-18	37	540
					TCA	1.0	67.6	18	4	103
					TCH	3.5	52.6	18	11	158
					TRE	18.3	44.2	17	32	360
S190901ap	23:31:01	BNS (86%)	241 ± 79	14753	GRANDMA	0.4	58.6	17-18	9.1	354
					TCA	1.25	57.4	18	2.5	100
					TCH	4.5	46.6	18	3.0	112
					TRE	0.4	48.6	17	7.2	279
S190814bv	21:10:39	NSBH (99%)	267 ± 52	23	GRANDMA	0.5	22.5	17-23	90.2	161
					TCA	0.65	13.5	18	21.9	32
					TRE	0.5	22.2	17	89.0	139
					LesMakes	1.3	3.6	18.5	6.1	2
					CFHT	232.0	0.5	23.0	< 1	1
S190718y ^a	14:35:12	BNS (2%)	227 ± 165	7246	GRANDMA	3.9	54.6	17-19	48.8	120
					TRE	7.4	51.1	17	48.8	120
					Shao/T60	4.6	1.3	16.5	< 1	< 1
					UBAI/T60	3.9	1.5	18.0	< 1	< 1
					Lisnyky/AZT-8	5.7	2.8	19.2	< 1	< 1
S190510g	02:59:39	BNS (42%)	227 ± 92	1166	GRANDMA	2.1	69.3	18	45.0	51
					TCA	16.7	54.7	18	0.3	24
					TCH	2.1	68.3	18	44.7	31
S190426c	15:21:55	BNS (24%)	377 ± 100	1131	GRANDMA	6.3	60.5	17-20	28.6	152
					TCA	7.4	52.9	18	9.7	23
					TCH	15.4	51.4	18	4.3	25
					TRE	7.4	50.9	17	14.0	105
					OAJ	6.3	4.9	19.6	11.4	44
S190425z	08:18:05	BNS (99%)	156 ± 41	7461	GRANDMA	6.7	63.4	17-23	2.8	135
					TCA	38.1	29.1	18.0	0.9	18.0
					TCH	22.4	47.7	18.0	1.0	25
					TRE	6.7	33.6	17.0	2.4	124
					Zadko	6.7	28.0	16.0	< 1	< 1
					Abastumani/T70	14.2	2.5	16.5	< 1	< 1
					Lisnyky/AZT-8	14.8	2.2	19.2	< 1	< 1
					Les Makes/T60	7.0	8.5	19.2	< 1	< 1
					GMG/2.4	9.3	3.0	19.0	< 1	< 1
					CAHA/2.2	81.6	1.7	23.0	< 1	< 1

2.2. Nobel Prize in Physics 2017

On October 3, the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences announced the laureates of the Nobel Prize in Physics for the year 2017. The award was given to three American scientists: Rainer Weiss, Barry C. Barish, and Kip S. Thorne for their 'decisive contributions to the LIGO detector project and the observation of gravitational waves' [3].

2.3. Calculations of Gravitational Wave Parameters

The amplitude of gravitational waves, like electromagnetic waves, decreases inversely proportional to the distance from the source, and the power decreases with the square of the distance. According to the general theory of relativity, a system of two masses, m_1 and m_2 , separated by a distance r , emits gravitational waves with a power of

$$P = -\frac{32}{5} \frac{G^4}{c^5} \frac{(m_1 m_2)^2 (m_1 + m_2)}{r^5},$$

where G is the gravitational constant, c is the speed of light in a vacuum. The negative sign indicates that the power is radiated rather than received from an external source. For the Sun-Earth system, this power is nearly 200 W [22].

The power of the Sun's electromagnetic radiation is approximately 3.86×10^{26} W. Theoretically, the energy loss due to gravitational radiation should eventually cause the Earth to fall into the Sun. However, the total energy of the Earth in orbit around the Sun (kinetic energy + gravitational potential energy) is nearly 1.14×10^{36} J, of which only 200 J per second is lost through gravitational radiation. This would minimally reduce the Earth's orbit radius by almost 1×10^{-15} m per day, or approximately the diameter of a proton. In this case, the Earth's spiral fall into the Sun would take about 10^{13} times longer than the current age of the Universe. Clearly, such estimates are meaningless, partly because the Sun and Earth undergo negligible changes in their masses over time. To calculate the time until the merger of two masses due to gravitational wave radiation, the theory provides the following expression:

$$t = \frac{5}{256} \frac{c^5}{G^3} \frac{r^4}{(m_1 m_2)(m_1 + m_2)}$$

Choosing a pair of neutron stars with masses equal to that of the Sun and an initial distance between them of 190,000 km, we obtain an orbital period of 1000 seconds and an expected lifespan of almost 400,000 years. Gravitational waves from such a system could only be observed by space interferometers, which are currently only in the planning stage. The power of gravitational radiation from such a binary system is 2×10^{23} W. At a distance of 40 light-years from Earth, the radiation flux would be approximately 10^{-17} W/cm², and from all double stars in our Galaxy, it would be only slightly higher, around $\sim 10^{-14}$ W/cm² of gravitational energy. The frequency of this radiation lies in the range of several tens of Hertz.

However, if the orbit of the binary neutron star system were to decrease to approximately 2000 km, the system's lifetime would be only 36 hours. The orbital frequency would change from 1 orbit per second initially to 900 orbits per second when the orbit shrinks to 20 km. If such a system were close enough to Earth, current instruments could detect its gravitational waves. However, such an event is extremely rare. Signals from binary neutron stars can come in a frequency range from a few Hz to approximately 1 kHz.

In conclusion, gravitational waves could exist at any frequency, but waves at very low (less than 0.001 Hz) and very high (above 10^9 Hz) frequencies are likely impossible to detect on Earth. Another example is the radiation from a pulsar in the Crab Nebula (distance 5500 light-years). Estimates suggest it emits gravitational waves with a power of almost 10^{31} W, resulting in a flux density on Earth, over vast distances to the source, of only 3×10^{-14} W/cm². [16, 17, 28-29]. However, the sensitivity of modern gravitational detectors is limited to values between 10^{-1} and 10^{-3} W/cm², at least 11 orders of magnitude less than needed.

Calculations' Conclusions:

The reason for the low power of gravitational waves lies in the small value of the gravitational constant, which is part of Newton's law of universal gravitation and Einstein's equations describing the generation of gravitational waves. The second reason is that dipole radiation is impossible for gravitational waves; instead, quadrupole radiation, weaker, is realized for them.

Large masses are characteristic of cosmic objects. Examples of cosmic gravitational wave sources include star-planet systems, binary stars, supernova explosions leading to the formation of neutron stars or black holes, or during their collisions. The flow of gravitational radiation generated during a supernova flash is approximately 10^{15} times greater than the flow from the nearest double star. In our Galaxy, supernovae flash, on average, once every 30 years. Therefore, one should expect to receive radiation from other galaxies: a sphere with a radius of almost 10 million light-years contains about 300 galaxies, and pulses of gravitational radiation with a flux density of 10^{-3} W/cm² are expected to arrive several times a year. However, this value is at the limit of sensitivity, and detecting such bursts of gravitational waves is challenging.

CONCLUSIONS

As we have come to understand, gravitational waves are an extremely intriguing phenomenon that deserves close observation. Thanks to gravitational waves, we can discover new astronomical objects and confirm various scientific theories, such as the general theory of relativity and the Big Bang theory. I believe that gravitational waves will help us gain a better understanding of the Universe, possibly bringing scientists closer to the development of new theories (such as a theory of everything). In this work, I analyzed data, performed calculations, and highlighted the direction of development in modern astrophysics and astronomy. For a deeper understanding of this topic, I joined the GRANDMA project and attended their lectures. I consider this project to be highly promising and worthy of attention.

1. For laboratory sources of gravitational waves, their power does not exceed 10^{20} W. To put this into perspective, this power is a thousand times smaller than the power of light that the human eye can detect. To increase the power of gravitational waves under laboratory conditions, it is necessary to increase the mass of radiating bodies and the rate of change of acceleration (jerk). However, increasing mass is limited to values between 1 and 10 tons, and increasing jerk results in the destruction of the body.

2. The power of gravitational wave radiation for two interacting bodies increases proportionally to the fifth power of the masses of the bodies, while the energy reservoir is proportional to the mass to the first power. This means that for large masses, the efficiency of gravitational wave radiation sharply increases.

3. Calculations show that a binary star system with each star having a mass of 1000 times that of the Sun, located at a distance of 100 million km, emits gravitational waves with a power of 3×10^{29} W (the energy of these stars is 3.6×10^{50} J). The speed of their approach is 2.5 mm/s. These stars are expected to merge in a million years, with only about 3×10^8 of the stars' energy being converted into the energy of gravitational waves.

4. A completely different scenario is expected when two black holes rotate around their common center of mass at a distance from each other approximately equal to the gravitational radius, and with an orbital velocity close to the speed of light. In this case, for bodies with the mass of the Sun (2×10^{30} kg), the gravitational radius is equal to 3 km, the angular rotation velocity is 10^5 s⁻¹ (approximately 16 kHz), and the power of radiation is about 1.4×10^{47} W. With a total rest energy of these bodies equal to 3.6×10^{47} J, approximately 10% of the rest energy of the stars will be converted into the energy of gravitational waves.

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